

Hamilton

Based on 2021 Census Data

City of Hamilton (CMA) Highlights

Population
= 785,184

Number of Homes
= 320,081

Population Density
= 571.8/Km²

5-year Population change = 5.0%

Age Distribution by Gender

33%
Age 55+

39%
Age 25-54

28%
Age 0-24

\$47,880
Average Income
(after-tax)

11.8%
Unemployment
Rate

Citizenship & Immigrant Population

Canadian Citizens

Immigrants

Recent Immigrants

Recent Immigrants by Birthplace

Immigrants by Birthplace

Language Spoken at Home

English | 84.6%
Non-official Languages | 11.3%

Highest Certificate, Diploma or Degree

■ No certificate, diploma or degree
■ Secondary (high) school diploma or equivalency
■ Postsecondary certificate, diploma or degree

Neighbourhood Homes

Average monthly shelter costs

Rent their home

Average home value

Major repair needed

Public Health
Agency of Canada

Agence de la santé
publique du Canada

Rebecca Ganann | ganann@mcmaster.ca
Caroline Moore | camoore@mcmaster.ca

Institute for
Research on Aging

Aging, Community
and Health
RESEARCH UNIT

LABARGE CENTRE FOR MOBILITY IN AGING

Cite

Siddiqui, S., Orr, E., Ganann, R. On behalf of the EMBOLDEN research team. (2023).
Infographic: Neighbourhood Profile-Hamilton.
URL: <https://emboldenstudy.mcmaster.ca/projects-results/>